

The 19 risk factors presented in Choetkiertikul et al. (2017) 'Predicting the delay of issues with due dates in software projects'. The second column provides a description of each factor as defined in the original paper. The third column presents our translation of the factor to epic-level and how we extracted it from ABC data.

Risk factor	Description of factor in original paper	How we translated and measured the factor at epic-level at ABC
1. Discussion time	The discussion time spent on finding solutions to solve the issue (time in days between states <i>Open</i> and <i>Development In Progress</i>)	The discussion time spent on the epic (time in days between the <i>Creation date</i> and <i>Start date of the development phase</i>)
2. Elapsed time from creation until prediction	Number of days from the creation date of the issue until prediction time	Number of days from the creation date of the epic until prediction time
3. Elapsed time from prediction until deadline	Number of days from prediction time until the due date of the issue	Number of days from prediction time until the <i>Planned delivery date</i> of the epic
4. Issue type	Type assigned to the issue (Task, Bug, New feature, Improvement, Function Test)	Type assigned to the epic (New Feature, Bug Fix, Improvement)
5. Number of repetition tasks	Number of times the issue was reopened after being closed	Total number of times a user story assigned to the epic was reopened after being closed
6. Developer involved with delayed issues	Number of delayed issues that the assigned developer is involved with to the total number of issues that the assigned developer is involved with	Median ratio of delayed epics that teams working on the epic are involved with to the total number of epics the teams are involved with
7. Developer's workload	Number of open issues assigned to the developer at a time	Median number of story points assigned to a developer working on the epic per sprint
8. Issue priority	Priority assigned to the issue (Blocker, critical, major, minor, trivial)	Priority assigned to the epic (Blocker, major, minor)
9. Changing of priority	Number of times the issue's priority has been changed	Number of times the epic's priority has been changed
10. Number of comments	Number of comments posted by developers on the issue	Number of comments posted by team members working on the epic
11. Number of fix versions	Number of release versions for which the issue will be fixed	Not applicable
12. Changing of fix versions	Number of times the fix versions associated with the issue have been changed	Not applicable
13. Number of affect versions	Number of release versions in which the issue has been found	Not applicable
14. Number of issue links	Number of links (relate to, duplicate, block) the issue has with other issues	Number of incoming and outgoing dependencies the epic has on other epics
15. Number of blocked issues	Number of other issues that are being blocked by the issue	Number of incoming dependencies from other epics for which the epic is blocking
16. Number of blocking issues	Number of other issues that block the issue from being completed	Number of outgoing dependencies on epics that are blocking
17. Topics of an issue's description	Set of 10 topics extracted from the issue's textual description using Latent Dirichlet Allocation	Set of 10 topics extracted from the epic's textual description using Latent Dirichlet Allocation
18. Changing of description	Number of times the issue's description has been changed	Number of times the epic's description has been changed
19. Reporter reputation	Reputation of the assigned developer, measured as the number of issues the developer has opened and fixed to the number of issues the developer has opened plus one	Median reputation of the developers working on the epic, measured as the number of epics the developer has been involved with and are set to being 'Completed' to the number of epics the developer has been involved with plus one